

Removal of Pharmaceuticals from Water Using Char Derived from Spent PVDF Membranes: Preliminary Modification Tests

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Abstract

The contamination of water systems by pharmaceuticals has become a growing environmental concern due to their potential risks and the challenges associated with their removal. Adsorption is widely recognized as an efficient and sustainable water treatment method, and alternative adsorbents have gained attention as substitutes for conventional materials. This study investigates the potential of modified chars derived from spent ultrafiltration membranes (MC) for the removal of ciprofloxacin from water. The produced MC exhibited a microporous structure with 344.64 m²/g surface area. Different modification techniques were applied: acid activation (AMC), alkali-acid activation (AAMC), and magnetization (MMC). AMC and MMC demonstrated the highest adsorption capacities (9.1 and 9.4 mg/g) and removal efficiencies (32.3 and 32.1%). Given their adsorption performance, these preliminary findings suggest that MC-based adsorbents could be a promising alternative material for water treatment.

Keywords

Activation; Adsorption; Alternative Adsorbents; Antibiotic; Ciprofloxacin; Water Treatment.

INTRODUCTION

The presence of pharmaceutical contaminants, such as ciprofloxacin antibiotic, in water systems represents a significant threat to human health and aquatic ecosystems as hazardous compounds even at low concentrations (Scaria *et al.*, 2021). Among the various approaches to address this critical issue, adsorption stands as a sustainable and efficient method for water treatment (Phoon *et al.*, 2020).

Aligned with the circular economy, alternative adsorbents have emerged as viable substitutes for conventional activated carbons (De Gisi *et al.*, 2016). In this context, a char derived from spent PVDF membranes was successfully developed through optimal pyrolysis conditions and shows promising characteristics for application in adsorption for water treatment (Da Silva *et al.*, 2024).

Activation and modification processes are crucial for enhancing the adsorption performance of chars by improving porosity, surface area, and adsorption capacity (Leng *et al.*, 2021). Activation can be physical, involving high-temperature oxidation (800-1000 °C), or chemical, using dehydrating agents (Panwar and Pawar, 2020). In modification methods, functional groups are introduced onto the char surface through oxidation, sulfidation, ammonification, or ligand anchoring (Demiral *et al.*, 2021). Despite their distinct purposes, activation and modification often have interchangeable terminology.

Several studies have explored the modification of chars to enhance their adsorption capacities for pharmaceutical removal from water using diverse precursors and modification techniques (Table 1).

Table 1. Some studies on char modifications for pharmaceutical removal

Char precursor	Modification technique	Pharmaceutical	Reference
Shells of <i>Sterculia villosa</i>	Acid activating by phosphoric acid and magnetizing with iron chloride and iron sulfate	Ciprofloxacin	Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2022)
Coffee bean husks	Acid activating by phosphoric acid	Diclofenac and Levofloxacin	Maged <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Municipal sludge	Acid activating by phosphoric acid and magnetizing with zinc chloride and iron chloride	Ciprofloxacin, Norfloxacin and Ofloxacin	Ma <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Municipal sewage sludge	Alkali-acid combined activating by sodium hydroxide and nitric acid or acetic acid	Tetracycline	Tang <i>et al.</i> (2018)

In this context, the present preliminary study investigates the potential application of modified membrane char (MC) for ciprofloxacin removal in water treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The membrane char (MC) used in the modification tests was produced from PVDF fibers obtained from a Suez ZW500 ultrafiltration membrane module, according to Da Silva *et al.* (2024). The fibers underwent cleaning, fragmentation (≈ 3 cm), and pyrolysis processes (584 °C; 111 min). The resulting MC was homogenized, ground (<149 μm), rinsed with ultrapure water, and dried (120 °C; 120 min).

Modification tests

MC modification tests were conducted by adapting and combining methodologies to enhance its properties as an adsorbent for water treatment (Table 2).

Table 2. Membrane char (MC) modification tests

Modification	Methodology	References
Acid activation (AMC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 75% phosphoric acid and MC (1:4 w/v ratio) Magnetic stirring (5 h; 80 °C) Hot water bath (2 h; 50 °C) Filtration and drying Furnace (111 min; 584°C; heating 5° C/min; N₂ atmosphere 0.06 L/min) Cooling (25 °C), washing, and drying (105 °C). 	Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2022) Ma <i>et al.</i> (2020) Maged <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Magnetization (MMC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.33 g of iron chloride, 1.83 g of iron sulfate, 2.5 g of MC and 100 mL of distilled water Magnetic stirring (1 h; 80 °C) 30 mL (stepwise) of 3M sodium hydroxide Magnetic stirring (5 h; 80 °C) Decantation, supernatant discard, washing, and drying (105 °C). 	Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2022) Ma <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Alkali-acid activation (AAMC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 200 mL of 2M sodium hydroxide and 2 g of MC Magnetic stirring (1 h; 90 °C) Hot water bath + Sonication (2 h; 50 °C) Filtration, washing, and drying 200 mL of 65% nitric acid and 2 g of MC Magnetic stirring (1 h; 25°C) Filtration, washing, and drying (105 °C). 	Tang <i>et al.</i> (2018)

Adsorption tests

Adsorption tests with modified MC samples (AMC, MMC, or AAMC) were conducted in glass bottles containing 50 mg of adsorbent and 50 mL of ciprofloxacin aqueous solution (30 ppm) and agitated in a shaker (200 rpm; 25 °C; 24 h). Subsequently, the samples were filtered through syringe filters, and final pharmaceutical concentrations were determined by UV-vis spectrophotometry at 271 nm. All tests were carried out in duplicate and the adsorption capacities and removal efficiencies were evaluated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 summarizes the characteristics of the membrane char (MC) produced for the modification tests to develop its adsorption performance in water treatment.

Table 3. Main characteristics of membrane char (MC), adapted from Da Silva *et al.* (2024)

Surface area	Surface morphology
344.64 m ² /g	
Porosity Microporous structure with an average pore diameter of 1.8 nm and a total pore volume of 0.16 cm ³ /g.	
Irregular flaky shapes, no compaction, and presence of pores on the surface of the particles.	
Functional groups	Crystalline structure
Absence of functional groups characteristics of PVDF fibers (e.g., C - F) and presence of functional groups typical of carbons (e.g., C = O).	Existence of both highly ordered graphitic and amorphous carbon structures.

The results of the adsorption capacity and removal efficiency of the MC-modified adsorbents produced in the modification tests for ciprofloxacin removal from water are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Adsorption capacity and removal efficiency of MC-modified adsorbents

MC-modified adsorbent	Adsorption capacity (mg/g)	Efficiency removal (%)
MC acid-activated (AMC)	9.13 ± 0.41	32.30 ± 1.47
MC magnetized (MMC)	9.42 ± 0.32	32.10 ± 1.93
MC alkali-acid activated (AAMC)	0.34 ± 0.01	1.57 ± 0.05

The results indicated that the modified materials showed potential for ciprofloxacin removal. Under the evaluated conditions, AMC and MMC demonstrated the highest adsorption capacities (9.1 and 9.4 mg/g) and removal efficiencies (32.3 and 32.1%), respectively. According to Zhang *et al.* (2019), the ciprofloxacin majority exists in zwitterionic form, with positive and negatively charged structures ($-NH_2^+$ and $-COO^-$ groups) at pH from 6.0 to 8.0, and its adsorption mainly occurs due to electrostatic attraction. This may explain the weak results of AAMC (0.3 mg/g and 1.6%) since acid- and alkali-activated sites must have blinded each other.

While preliminary, these findings highlight the potential of the produced materials as an alternative to conventional activated carbons, particularly the MMC due to its magnetic recovery capability provided by iron impregnation.

CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary findings of this study suggest that the adsorbents derived from the modified membrane char represent a promising alternative for the adsorption of pharmaceuticals. The results demonstrated the feasibility of reusing waste to develop innovative materials with potential applications in water treatment. Nevertheless, to improve the material's adsorption efficiency, propose the adsorption's mechanism, and describe the adsorption system, additional tests must be performed such as evaluating pH conditions, adsorbent dosage, kinetics (contact time), isotherm (initial concentration), and thermodynamics (temperature). Further research on composite synthesis and performance evaluation for broader applications with co-contaminants and/or real aqueous matrices is also relevant.

REFERENCES

- Da Silva, I. P., Maged, A., Abreu, V. P. L., Candido, A. L. Q., Rocha, S. D. F., De Paula, E. C. (2024). Transfiguration of discarded PVDF ultrafiltration membranes: Optimization of pyrolysis parameters for high-value char production. *Waste Management*, **190**, 360-369.
- De Gisi, S., Lofrano, G., Grassi, M., Notarnicola, M. (2016). Characteristics and adsorption capacities of low-cost sorbents for wastewater treatment: A review. *Sustainable Materials and Technologies*, **9**, 10-40.
- Demiral, İ., Samdan, C., Demiral, H. (2021). Enrichment of the surface functional groups of activated carbon by modification method. *Surfaces and Interfaces*, **22**, 100873.
- Kumar, A., Patra, C., Kumar, S., Narayanasamy, S. (2022). Effect of magnetization on the adsorptive removal of an emerging contaminant ciprofloxacin by magnetic acid activated carbon. *Environmental Research*, **206**, 112604.
- Leng, L., Xiong, Q., Yang, L., Li, H., Zhou, Y., Zhang, W., Jiang, S., Li, H., Huang, H. (2021). An overview on engineering the surface area and porosity of biochar. *Science of the Total Environment*, **763**, 144204.
- Ma, Y., Li, P., Yang, L., Wu, L., He, L., Gao, F., Qi, X., Zhang, Z. (2020). Iron/zinc and phosphoric acid modified sludge biochar as an efficient adsorbent for fluoroquinolones antibiotics removal. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, **196**, 110550.
- Maged, A., Dissanayake, P. D., Yang, X., Pathirannahalage, C., Bhatnagar, A., Ok, Y. S. (2021). New mechanistic insight into rapid adsorption of pharmaceuticals from water utilizing activated biochar. *Environmental Research*, **202**, 111693.
- Panwar, N. L., Pawar, A. (2020). Influence of activation conditions on the physicochemical properties of activated biochar: A review. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, 1-23.
- Phoon, B. L., Ong, C. C., Saheed, M. S. M., Show, P. L., Chang, J. S., Ling, T. C., Lam, S. S., Juan, J. C. (2020). Conventional and emerging technologies for removal of antibiotics from wastewater. *Journal of hazardous materials*, **400**, 122961.
- Scaria, J., Anupama, K. V., Nidheesh, P. V. (2021). Tetracyclines in the environment: An overview on the occurrence, fate, toxicity, detection, removal methods, and sludge management. *Science of the Total Environment*, **771**, 145291.
- Tang, L., Yu, J., Pang, Y., Zeng, G., Deng, Y., Wang, J., Ren, X., Ye, S., Peng, B., Feng, H. (2018). Sustainable efficient adsorbent: alkali-acid modified magnetic biochar derived from sewage sludge for aqueous organic contaminant removal. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, **336**, 160-169.
- Zhang, H.; Khanal, S. K.; Jia, Y.; Song, S.; Lu, H. (2019). Fundamental insights into ciprofloxacin adsorption by sulfate-reducing bacteria sludge: Mechanisms and thermodynamics. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, **378**, 122103.